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Colonialism, Leadership Issues, and Arrested Development of African States: An Appraisal

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Abstract

In the post-colonial era, African states have faced a myriad of leadership issues ranging from poor leadership, leadership failures, lack of strategic vision and corruption. Whether by design or by chance, these issues have not bided well for these societies. In some cases, their processes of development have become convoluted. In others, the leadership issues have led to situations of arrested development. The paper utilized secondary sources such as textbooks, publish Journals Articles, and internet sources to do content analysis and qualitative analysis of the data. The paper notes that the exploitative nature of colonialism, and the desire of former colonial masters to hang on to their former colonies by any means possible have attended to these leadership issues, and has made them protracted. In particular, the self-serving attitude of the African elites and the lack of patriotism have exacerbated these problems. What is needed is a total reorientation so that meaningful progress can be made in these countries.

Keywords: Colonialism, Leadership, Imperialism, Development and Dependency

Introduction

African states in the post-colonial era have been faced with a glut of leadership issues, which have contributed in no small measure to the developmental problems faced by them. These leadership issues have given rise to rampant political instability and corruption, civil wars, insurrections, and other forms of conflict. In the western media, Africa has become synonymous with humanitarian crises, whether man-made or otherwise. In the 1980s, for instance, a brutal civil war in Sierra Leone left thousands dead and many more wounded and displaced. Similarly, in Liberia, within the same time period, civil war tore the country apart and claimed the lives of many. In the Central

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African Republic (CAR), intermittent clashes between ethnic and religious militias destroyed the lives of many civilians. In North Africa, the Arab Spring that started in Tunisia spread through Libya and Egypt, accompanied by regime changes there. This chronicle of regime changes shows that many of the countries on the African continent are embroiled in dire situations of political instability, as poor leadership often provides the impetus for violent regime change. Poor leadership, in turn, may not be unconnected with the continent's colonial past.

In 2022, after the ouster of Omar Bashir, Sudan descended into a military conflict that pitted the military government against a paramilitary unit. The conflict has claimed many lives, and thousands have been displaced. South Sudan is a case of the type of leadership issues that have plagued the African continent. After gaining independence from Sudan in 2011 through a UN-monitored referendum, the new country soon descended into an armed conflict between two factions: one supporting the president, the other his deputy. The conflict has slowed the pace of development and caused aid donors to shift their financial assistance to more stable regions.

The litany of political instability and violent regime change has not abated. Within the second quarter of 2023, military coups took place first in Niger, then in Mali. The coup in Mali removed the democratically elected president. A military coup also took place in Gabon and followed the pattern of the others. Omar Bongo, who had ruled the country for decades, was removed by soldiers after a flawed election. Most of these violent regime changes are blamed on poor leadership and a lack of transparency. For instance, in Gabon, the Bongo family had been in power for four decades in a kind of sit-tight arrangement that had failed to produce meaningful progress in the country. The leadership problems on the continent have produced, in their wake, bad governance, which has in turn given rise to many forms of rebellion such as militancy, insurgency, insurrection, and corruption (Essoh 2019, Achebe 1984). The continent's colonial experience and its aftermath may not be unconnected with these leadership issues.

Colonialism Defined

Colonialism is the establishment, maintenance, acquisition, and expansion of colonies in one territory by a foreign power. This may be done through sheer military prowess, threats or coercion, the use of treaties, or forceful annexation. It is the process whereby a foreign power claims sovereignty over a territory and proceeds to change or alter the

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structure, government, and economics of the territory. These are done without the active consent and participation of the people in the colony. Colonialism is therefore a form of temporary, extended domination by people over other people. It is a reflection and part of the historical universe of intergroup domination, subjugation, oppression, and exploitation (Bergesen, 1980). Based on this perspective, the history of the capitalist world economy is a history of colonialism, meaning that there have always been attempts by the core to create a periphery and control it politically in order to exploit it economically (Benjamin, 2007).

In determining the period of colonial dominance, the common practice among scholars has been to take the year of formal declaration of a colony as the starting point. Some think this legalistic approach does not quite capture the essence of colonialism and is therefore inadequate (Ziltener and Kunzler, 2013). Since political domination by a foreign power over a given territory or parts of it is generally adjudged a critical aspect of colonialism, the takeoff point may be when sovereignty is *ipso facto* declared over the given territory. In Nigeria, the colony of Lagos was established by Britain in 1863. Before then, the Royal Niger Company was active in trade and other commercial activities in the area. In 1878, the company applied for and received a charter from the British Government to conduct a semi-administration in the Nigerian territories to facilitate trade. The Nigerian territories later became protectorates of the British government. Some authorities refer to this arrangement as semi-colonialism or indirect rule because there was little interference in local affairs. The Native Authorities System (the pre-runner of Nigeria's local government system) came into existence during this period. Writers on the subject matter have not agreed on what should be regarded as the take-off point of colonialism in Nigeria. Afigbo (1972) fixed the date at 1891, while Ziltener and Kunzler (2013) preferred an earlier date of 1851. The result of all of these and, based on the nature of political domination as already explained, the generally accepted date of 1900 as the take-off point of colonialism in Nigeria may not be sustained.

The Native Authorities System recorded varying degrees of success in different parts of the country. In northern Nigeria, where the Hausa-Fulani had already established a centralised system of political administration, indirect rule recorded a high degree of success. Colonial officials made use of the traditional political authorities (Obas and Emirs) to implement indirect rule. Colonial policies were passed through the

authorities to the people. In the Yoruba areas, although the monarchical-traditional system was centralised, it was more democratic than in Northern Nigeria, where the Emir was revered and his word was law. The *Oyomesi-in-council* and the people could challenge the power and authority of the Oba if they thought his actions were outside the statutory powers allotted to him. The democratic nature of the Yoruba traditional system could be seen in the Egba Women demonstrations of 1947. The Abeokuta women embarked on a series of peaceful demonstrations against the taxation of women and children by the native authorities on behalf of the colonial government. These demonstrations led to a review of the taxation policy in Abeokuta and the abdication of Oba Ladipo Ademola in 1949.

In the Niger Delta and southeastern parts of the country where a centralised traditional political system was lacking, British colonial officials were in a quandary. The pre-colonial political systems of these areas could be best described as republican and acephalous, respectively. In the former, the people practiced direct democracy, similar to the ancient Greeks. In the latter, political power resided among powerful groups such as community leaders, youth groups, and women groups, who exercised such powers for the benefit of the community. British colonial officials remedied the situation by appointing Warrant Chiefs – so-called because their powers emanated from the warrants or licences that were issued to them. The excesses and abuse of power of the Warrant Chiefs are well documented (Afigbo, 1972). These excesses led to the Aba women's riot of 1929. Many reasons have been adduced for the adoption of indirect rule, among which is the fact that it was inexpensive compared to direct rule. There was also a dearth of personnel, making the adoption of indirect rule a child of necessity. The prevalence of tropical diseases such as malaria and typhoid made the continent “the white man's grave.” Many Europeans were not willing to risk life and limb to serve the Empire. In the first half of the 20th century, Britain was involved in two world wars. It had to even recruit personnel from its colonies to help prosecute the wars.

Nature of Colonialism

The Berlin Conference, which later came to be known as “the scramble for Africa” by modern historians, was convened by German Chancellor Otto Von Bismarck in 1886. Until then, European powers were wont to clash with one another over areas of control or influence. Such clashes led to the Boer Wars between the Dutch and British settlers in

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South Africa in the late 19th century. The conference provided a systematic order for the plundering of the continent. Major European powers such as Germany, Britain, France, Spain, and Portugal, and, to a lesser extent, Italy, all indicated their areas of control and influence on the African continent. The primary objective of colonialism was to establish control over the colonies using warfare, threats of force, and making treaties with the African chiefs. Once political control was achieved, economics became the main concern. Colonialism is a process whereby a foreign power claims or takes over a territory belonging to other peoples and then proceeds to change the government, economics, and social structure of the colony. It is a set of unequal or asymmetrical relationships between a foreign power and the indigenous population.

The consensus among African historians is that colonialism was morally wrong. Its legacies, particularly the negative ones, continue to influence the pace of development and have contributed to the myriad of developmental issues besetting the continent. Colonialism had two main objectives. The first, and in no particular order, was the exploration of new lands for food and raw materials for European industries. The silk route stretched from China in the Far East, through India and the Middle East into Europe. Contrary to a widely held belief, food was not an adjunct to British imperial adventure but fundamental to it (Collingham, 2017). Where food was plentiful, it laid the groundwork for settler colonialism, like it did in New Zealand, where shoals of fish off its coast encouraged British seafarers to settle there (Collingham, 2017). Kenya also attracted European settlers because of its highlands, which proved suitable for cultivating quality tea. In Africa, a widely held view is that empire-building preceded trade. In actuality, it was the other way round. "Trade began the empire" (The Economist, 2017:80). After the abolition of slave trade in the 1800s, British merchants turned to trade in commodities such as palm produce, cocoa, rubber, hide and skins. Palm oil lubricated machines in the factories. Cocoa was made into chocolates and allied products. Hide and skin were made into shoes, belts, hand-bags and suitcases.

From favourable reports that Africa was fertile ground for the spread of Christianity, Christian missionaries followed in the wake of trade. For instance, the Reverend Hope Waddel arrived at Calabar in 1844 from Jamaica, where he was stationed. The Scottish missionary, Mary Slessor, was already active in the area, where she vigorously campaigned against the killing of twins. In 1878, the Royal Niger Company applied for a charter from the British government to organise a semi-

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administration in the Nigerian territories, ostensibly to facilitate trade. The charter was granted, and it laid the groundwork for full-fledged British colonial rule in Nigeria, which began in 1878. The other objective of colonialism, which was also of an economic nature, was the exploration of new markets for European-made goods and products. Raw materials in the colonies were extracted at rock-bottom prices. British merchants alone decided what prices to pay for the commodities. The local producers had little say in the matter. And the prices they were paid did not reflect the internationally determined prices for these commodities. These raw materials were then taken to Europe, manufactured into finished products, brought back, and sold at exorbitant prices in the colonies. In Nigeria, an item like the locally produced gin (Okokoro) was declared contraband by colonial officials. Both the producers and sellers were subject to arrest and imprisonment. All of these were so British rum and whiskey could sell. This was the political economy of colonial rule.

The European powers needed raw materials for their industries, and the way the African economies were organised could not ensure a steady supply of these raw materials. This necessitated the direct take-over and control of the economies of African states (Ocheni and Nwankwo, 2012). It was important not only to acquire the raw materials but to acquire them in sufficient quantities. Colonial officials and European merchants therefore emphasised the cultivation of the required cash crops, such as palm produce, cocoa, rubber, hides and skins. Food sufficiency for the African population was a secondary consideration, although, in fairness to colonial rule, many African societies were able to attain a measure of food sufficiency better than it is presently.

The role of the African economy and states in the world market continues to be the production of primary goods and agricultural products, while the West controls the production of manufactured goods (Ocheni and Nwankwo, 2012). Until this imbalance is addressed, the African economy and, indeed, development on the continent will continue at a slow pace.

Colonialism was very undemocratic. The system was usually imposed on a people by a superior foreign power through the threat of war or coercion. The colonising power would proceed to alter the existing political and economic system without input or participation by the people being colonised. In Nigeria, for instance, at the amalgamation of the Northern and Southern Protectorates and the Colony of Lagos into one political entity in 1914, the Legislative Council that was formed had 27 members.

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The six Africans that were on it as ex-officio members had no voting power. It was the constitution that was introduced by Sir Arthur Richards in 1954 that introduced regionalism. The country was divided into three regions, and elections were conducted into the regional legislatures. One could argue that the undemocratic nature of colonialism may have unwittingly contributed to the level of political instability in many of the countries in the post-colonial era, simply because the people in these countries have no democratic role model to look back to. They are yet to imbibe democratic political culture because colonialism did not teach them anything close to it. Aside from the fact that political institutions in these countries are still young, consensus-building and a political culture that favours the common good are still difficult to attain.

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework adopted in this paper is dependency theory. The theory was developed in response to modernization theory, which postulated, among other things, a dichotomy between traditionalism and modernity achieved through structural differentiation (Talcott Parsons, Neil Smelser), an increase in production and capital investments (Rostow), and an enhancement of the capacity of the political system and institutions (Almond, Coleman, and Huntington). On the political front, these scholars were primarily concerned with the absence of political culture and the weakness of political institutions. Probably the most vexing part of modernization theory was its use of the so-called modernising elites, or the countries of North America and Europe, as standards for developing economies to follow. Dependency theory rejected these claims, particularly the notion that developing economies should follow the same path to development that their European counterparts had followed. The landscape has simply changed, and the goal-post keeps moving (Cardoso, 1976).

Dependency theory classified the world system into a core or centre (made up of industrialised nations) and the periphery (made up of colonised and developing economies). The theory argues that the export of capitalism to other parts of the world and its resultant colonialism and neo-colonialism is responsible for the underdevelopment and dependency of Third World economies. Besides, dependency theorists argue, the European powers became prosperous on the backs of their developing counterparts through the search for cheap raw materials, cheap labour, and markets for the finished products. The resulting colonialism and subsequent neo-

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colonialism meant that the resources of the colonized were and are still being exploited (Ake 1981, Rodney 1972, Nkrumah 1965, Frank 1967, Baran 1973). Dependency theory encapsulates the central argument of this discourse as it positions that underdevelopment and dependency in the Third World is a direct consequence of the development of the advanced industrialised nations of Europe and North America, who exploited the resources of the former through colonialism and lately, through neo-colonialism, by their incorporation into the world capitalist system at a subjugated position.

Literature Review

Colonialism on the African continent was exploitative and brutal. In *The Histories of the Hanged*, David Anderson wrote about the Mau Mau uprising in Kenya and the brutal response of the British colonial government there. During the period of the emergency rule from 1957 to 1960, people were taken into detention camps, tortured, and sometimes summarily executed. Anderson's work helped victims of the Mau Mau saga to win compensation in the British High Court (New African, 2014:40). It also led to a "statement of regret" from then-British Prime Minister David Cameron. There was also a systematic programme of extermination of the Herero people in present-day Namibia, which was then a German colony. According to Hiribarren (2014:42), "it was less a massacre with weapons, it was more about letting them starve behind what was called the "red line." It was genocide."

Studying the impacts of colonialism worldwide, Ziltener and Kunzler (2013:300) observed that there were differences in the levels of socio-economic development in colonised and non-colonised areas. In particular, the few non-colonised areas in Africa and Asia experienced less intensive modes of integration into the world economic system and a slower disruption and disintegration of the traditional social structures compared to colonial economies (Dixon, 1999b:57). Colonialism was heterogeneous, affecting different societies in different ways. Except in settler colonies, the average effect of colonialism on development in Africa seems to be negative (Heldring and Robinson, 2012). Neo-colonialism is the continuation of imperialism. Those who practice it do so without responsibility, and those who are exploited suffer from it without redress (Nkrumah, 1965).

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That being said, colonialism should not be blamed for all the ills of the African continent. Take the transatlantic slave trade, for instance. European slavers did not go into the hinterland to capture people and sell them into slavery. The African chiefs and people did it. But this is where the narrative diverges. Inhuman treatment, torture, and other forms of humiliation were not accepted practices on the African continent compared to Europe, where, for centuries, vanquished people were exposed to all manners of maltreatment as their conquerors saw fit. The Africans could not have imagined the horrors of the transatlantic crossing that those who were sold into slavery endured. In the New World, slaves were subjected to all manners of ill-treatment and humiliations. Even after slavery was abolished, people of African descent endured racial segregation and Jim Crow laws in the United States. They could not vote, and other civil liberties were denied them. In the 21st century, African Americans continue to lose their lives in the hands of racist policemen.

In many parts of the African continent, indentured people, whether captured in war or bought as slaves, were often treated humanely. And this was the mistaken belief of the Africans when they sold their kiths and kins into slavery. In some African communities, the captured were often integrated into society. In places like Opobo and Old Calabar in Nigeria's Niger Delta, slaves administered their masters' businesses and sometimes married into the family as part of the integration process. Some, like King Jaja of Opobo, rose to prominence as a result of this. In old Calabar, the Irish missionary Reverend Hope Waddell, who was posted to Calabar from Jamaica in 1844, recounted his experiences. He built churches and schools and persuaded the chiefs and people of Old Calabar to send their children to the schools. They sent their slaves instead, due to a mistrust of western education. For a long time, former slaves became better read and educated in society.

The philosophy of colonialism was encapsulated in "The White Man's Burden," a reference to a line in Rudyard Kipling's poem that was published in 1899. The "White Man's Burden" was made up of the three "Cs" of colonialism: civilization, Christianity, and commerce." The notion was that Europe had a noble responsibility, if not an obligation, to civilise the backward societies of Africa. In Kipling's view, the Africans had to be pulled towards the "light" so that they could see the error of their savage nature. The prevalence of this type of thinking was also evident in Joseph Conrad's "Heart of Darkness." It became the perfect excuse for the rape and plunder of a continent.

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Impacts of Colonialism

The impacts of colonialism on the African continent are at once political, economic, and social. As already alluded to in this paper, colonialism was undemocratic because it was imposed by a foreign power on unsuspecting people after treaties were signed by the local authorities. The indigenous people were ruled almost against their wishes. The widespread political instability on the African continent could be a pointer to the fact that colonial rule was not a model for democracy. People in former colonies simply could not look back to colonialism as a democratic role model. The democratic culture is lacking, as could be seen in rigged elections, manipulations of election results, and corruption. There may be other variables to explain this, but colonial rule did nothing to inculcate a democratic culture.

Colonial governments practiced “divide and rule”. Given the lack of capacity and the strong emphasis on law and order, all forms of colonial rule engaged in “divide and rule” by implementing policies that intentionally weakened indigenous power networks and institutions. European powers often played one nation or kingdom against another. This tactic made it easier for the European powers to gain control of particular areas. Once colonial rule was established, colonial governments often accentuated differences between ethnic groups, making them suspicious of one another. The tactic of “divide and rule” helped to establish a political system that promoted divisions based on ethnicity rather than unity based on a common national identity. In Nigeria, for instance, with the amalgamation policy of 1914, whereby the Northern and Southern protectorates and the colony of Lagos were merged and the country became a single political entity, different areas were administered separately based on language, culture, ethnicity, and religion. The consequences of this policy are many. Firstly, post-colonial ethnic conflicts in many parts of Africa tend to have their roots in this colonial policy because this policy often creates and exacerbates group differences. The policy also widened primordial cleavages. Secondly, in a multi-ethnic nation like Nigeria, national integration and nation-building become difficult because diverse groups owe their loyalty first to their groups and only secondly to the nation.

The issue of artificial boundaries is also of critical importance. It is a well-known fact that the boundaries of many post-colonial African states were drawn by the colonial powers to suit their purposes. As a result, diverse peoples were thrown together into what they see as an artificial contraption of the colonial metropole that does not deserve

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their loyalty and commitment. In many post-colonial multi-ethnic societies, the state machinery comes to be dominated by a single communal group or a coalition of a few communal groups that are unresponsive to the needs and yearnings of other groups in society. This situation tends to strain the social fabric of society and breed fragmentation and protracted social conflict (Azar, 1990). This has been the situation in Sudan that led to a UN-backed and sponsored referendum and resulted in the independence of South Sudan in July 2011.

There are two dimensions to the artificial border phenomenon: the creation of ethnically fragmented countries and the separation of the same people into bordering countries (Alesina et al., 2006:2). With the introduction of taxation in many African colonies, the state became seen as an oppressive and exploitative force. Ekeh (1975:92) believed that the roots of Nigeria's corruption could be traced to the days of colonialism, when African peoples had little identification with the colonial bureaucracy. Ekeh (1975:92) used the theory of the two publics to buttress his stand. Educated Africans tend to be citizens of two public realms and one private realm. The two publics are the amoral civic public and the moral primordial public. The concept of the state is encapsulated in the civic public, while the primordial public refers to non-state groupings. Citizens expect benefits from the civic public but give grudgingly back to it, while they are expected to give differentially to the primordial public without any benefits in return.

The economic impacts of colonialism are no less profound than the political ones. In many parts of Africa, colonial rule was used to support the activities of European firms and merchants in their quest for raw materials. African farmers were encouraged (even forced) to cultivate cash crops such as cocoa, rubber, and palm fruits. These, including hides and skins, were expropriated at rock-bottom prices for export to the colonial metropole. The prices paid did not reflect the internationally determined market prices for these products but were based on what the merchants were willing to pay. As a result, the local producers were denied the economic empowerment that their products were supposed to bring. The nature of capitalist exploitation also meant that finished products from the raw materials were brought back to the colonies for sale at exorbitant prices. Many years after independence, many African countries are still engaged in the production of primary goods and agricultural raw materials. They are also consumers of foreign-manufactured goods.

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Plantations were a critical aspect of the colonial economy. According to Ziltener and Kunzler (2013:300),” the development of a plantation economy required expropriation, which took place in different forms, implying more or less displacement of the indigenous population." The plantation economy took place in many parts of the colonial world, such as Kenya, India, and British Ceylon (Sri Lanka). Work migrations took place in relation to the plantations, but in general, working and living conditions were bad. Plantation owners relied on forced labour and debt strategies to indenture the workers, to the point that working on plantations became similar to modern slavery.

The social impacts of colonialism revolved around education, healthcare, and religion. Human capital development has remained one of the positive contributions of colonialism to long-term growth in Sub-Saharan Africa (Bolt and Bezemer, 2009). However, education under the colonial government was meant to recruit and train clerks, interpreters, and officials for colonial administration. “Education policies were guided by the practical needs of the colonial society” (Ziltener and Kunzler, 2013:300). Colonial education was western education. It was not rooted in African culture and therefore had no organic linkages to it (Ocheni and Nwankwo, 2012). It was literary in nature, without a technological base, and quite unsuitable for real or industrial development. In Nigeria, the colonial government did not make use of the educated elites in its administration except for a few who were used as clerks and interpreters. These educated elites formed themselves into a sort of opposition and were quite vociferous in criticising and condemning colonial policies. Their activities contributed in no small measure to the eventual achievement of self-rule.

Christianity enabled the indigenous peoples to convert to the religion of the colonisers. In some parts of the colonial world, missionaries came before the colonisers. For instance, the Rev. Hope Waddel of the Church of Scotland arrived in Old Calabar in 1844 from Jamaica, where he was stationed. The missionaries took pains not to be too close to the colonisers so as not to be labelled as an ally of foreign rule. The new religion demanded commitment from the natives and the renunciation of traditional practices such as ancestral worship, polygamy, and promiscuity. Missionary work was more successful in areas where “Native Churches” were groomed to carry on the task of preaching and winning souls. Also notable is the fact that the missions complemented the work of the colonial governments in education by building schools and hospitals. Healthcare under colonial governments was rudimentary and sparse, being limited to

dispensaries and cottage hospitals. The missionaries complemented the efforts of the colonial administrations in this area.

Imperialism and Neo-colonialism

Neo-colonialism is the continuation of colonialism by other means. It is the practice whereby powerful states (most often former colonial masters) indirectly dominate less powerful or vulnerable countries through economic, political, and cultural manipulations. Unlike classic colonialism, there is no direct political and economic control or territorial acquisition. Neo-colonialism is subtler and more indirect, unlike classic colonialism. But both are driven by the imperialist desire for expansion and profit from overseas ventures. In *Neo-colonialism: The Last Stage of Imperialism*, Nkrumah (1965) noted that African countries had begun to be subjected to new forms of colonialism, waged by their former colonialists and other developed nations. According to Nkrumah (1965), the struggle against neo-colonialism is aimed at preventing the financial power of the developed countries from being used in such a way as to impoverish the developing ones.

Neo-colonialism and imperialism on the African continent can be seen against the backdrop of the formation of the Organisation of African Unity (now the AU). On the one hand, the Casablanca Group was led by pan-Africanists like Kwame Nkrumah and Ben Bella of Algeria. They argued that African unity must be formed based on continued support for those countries still under the yoke of colonialism or any other form of political domination. The Pan-Africanists advocated for a single market with loose borders and a complete break with former colonial masters as a way for the continent to move forward. On the other hand, there was the Monrovia Group, led by William Tubman of Liberia and Felix Houghout-Boigny of Ivory Coast. They favoured a confederal system, looser borders, and maintaining strong economic ties with former colonial masters. The resulting OAU charter became a compromise between the two groups and resulted in a new era of exploitation and domination by rich countries.

At the time of independence, former colonial powers were eager to maintain control of their former colonies. They did this via trade, political control, and other bilateral relations. Former colonial masters became the preferred or even number one trading partners to their former colonies. The terms of trade and balance of payments were often unequal. Former colonies in Africa continue to be primary producers of raw

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materials and importers of finished products. A kind of dependency became engendered, with the poorer countries still adversely affected. Dependency, although a Marxist theory, views development and underdevelopment as the inevitable outcomes of the World Capitalist System and its inherent contradictions and exploitations (Ake, 1981). The theory argues that the export of capital by the West to other parts of the world and the colonialism and neo-colonialism engendered are responsible for the underdevelopment and dependency of the Third World (Nkrumah, 1965). Colonialism and neo-colonialism helped to incorporate the economies of the colonised peoples into the world capitalist system in a subjugated position, with the following consequences: development in the industrialised capitalist world and underdevelopment and dependency in the former colonised societies. As long as former colonial masters continue to manipulate the political and economic conditions necessary for development, developing economies will not be able to create large markets necessary for industrialization (Nkrumah, 1965). The current state of stagnation and arrested development will continue.

A clever means that former colonial masters used to prevent land reforms and redistribution of wealth has been the “willing buyer, willing seller” principle, which in most cases was written into the post-colonial constitutions of some African states. This happened in South Africa, Namibia, and Zimbabwe. Particularly in settled former colonies, this principle means that for lands that were confiscated from the indigenous peoples without compensation, the present occupants of those lands have to be willing to sell them to the original owners or their descendants. And even if they are willing to sell, the original owners have to be able to buy at a price fixed by the illegal occupants of those lands. As a result, in Zimbabwe, despite being less than 1% of the population, whites owned about 70% of the best lands (Economist, 2000:39). In South Africa, twenty-three years after the end of apartheid, the economy is still largely white-dominated. White households earn five times more than black households (Dludlu, 2017:33). People of Caucasian descent, who make up only 8.9% of the population, still control 87% of the land, compared to 13% allocated to the African indigenous people, who make up 79.2% of the population (Pheko, 2013:42).

The International Monetary Fund (IMF) and the International Bank for Reconstruction and Development (World Bank) were established in 1945 to help rebuild the devastated economies of post-World War II Europe and Japan. They were to provide financial advice and funding, promote trade, and make timely reports on these issues to

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Godwin Edet Essoh

the affected countries. With the help of America's Marshall Plan, both the IMF and the World Bank largely accomplished their missions. When it came to the emerging economies of Africa, the narrative changed. These institutions became instruments of neo-colonialism for domination, exploitation, and subjugation. The IMF and the World Bank did support development in the Third World by giving loans and grants for projects such as rural electrification, healthcare, clean water provision, and infrastructure. However, the conditionalities that were attached to these loans tended to do more harm than good to the economies of these countries. Firstly, the interest rates on these loans tended to be high, and the conditions for servicing the loans were often designed in such a way that the beneficiary countries found it difficult to fulfil them. Many of these countries have had to spend many years and billions of dollars to service their debt and arrears, to the point that their economies have become crippled.

Colonial rule had carved out small, non-viable states from what were formerly "united colonial territories." These vulnerable and unviable states found it difficult to independently develop on their own and must depend on their former colonial master for defence and to even maintain internal order. Even their economic and financial systems are tied to the apron strings of their former colonial masters. Often, there are bilateral treaties that protect these privileges. Military aid and the provision of internal security provide former colonial powers with the excuse they need to intervene in the political affairs of their former colonies. In 2000, Britain sent a military force into Sierra Leone to help protect the capital, Freetown, from being overrun by rebel forces. In 2014, France sent military troops into conflict zones in its former colonies to repel a Jihadist incursion in Mali and to quell ethno-religious warfare in the Central African Republic (CAR). France went on to propose a 3,000-strong counter-terrorism force to be based in Chad's capital, N'Djamena, to service five countries: Burkina Faso, Chad, Mali, Mauritania, and Niger, all former colonies. France had maintained a permanent garrison in Senegal for years. In December 2023, France decided to pull its remaining troops from Mali after disagreement with the country's government (Economist, July 2014:25). The fight against terrorism has provided former colonial masters and other powerful nations with the excuse and impetus to maintain their grip of political dominance over less powerful nations and former colonies.

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Pliant and failed leadership

In "The Black Man's Burden," Basil Davidson (1992) argued that when former colonial masters were granting self-rule to their former colonies, they made sure that they handed the countries over to a crop of leaders who would make the former colonies safe for further exploitation. In other words, the pliant and failed leadership witnessed on the African continent did not happen by chance but had been part of the neo-colonial agenda of the rich countries. At the dawn of independence, western countries applied their "planned regime" strategy (Pheko, 2013:42). From the liberation struggles, they designated leaders they regarded as "extremist" and those who were "moderates". By "moderates," western powers meant leaders who would protect their foreign economic and political interests at the expense of their own people. The "extremists" were regarded as subversives who were unreliable and who could not be trusted to do the bidding of western powers. It did not help the course of an African leader if he had a mind of his own, if he was visionary, or if he had a socialist bent.

According to Pheko (2013:43), "if an African leader is not favoured by Western powers, he is the wrong leader for democracy. If he or she wins elections, they are illegitimate." From the 1960s onward, many African leaders who were deemed unsuitable by Western powers were systematically eliminated or removed from their positions, even if these leaders meant well for their people. Congo's first Prime Minister, Patrice Lumumba, was assassinated by the secret service of some Western powers because they perceived him as a threat to western economic and political interests in the Congo (Witte, 2021). His hand-picked successor, Mobutu Sese Seko, became a despot and, with the connivance of western interests, plundered the Congo until he was removed from power by a rebel movement. In Ghana, a rebellion was stirred up against the pan-Africanist Kwame Nkrumah that removed him from power. He was succeeded by a line of corrupt army generals until Jerry Rawlings put Ghana back on the road to good governance. In Burkina Faso, the enigmatic and visionary Thomas Sankara was eliminated in mysterious circumstances, ostensibly by his military compatriots. His deputy, Blaise Campoare, ruled the country for about two decades until a popular uprising drove him from power.

About a decade after winning independence, Robert Mugabe and his ZANU-PF government undertook an ambitious land reform programme in Zimbabwe. The aim was to restore land that was forcibly taken without compensation to the original owners

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in Zimbabwe. Mugabe was denounced and demonized in every western capital. The western world embarked on a series of economic sanctions against the people of Zimbabwe in an attempt to force Mugabe to capitulate. The sanctions crippled the economy of Zimbabwe. According to Mbeki (2013), the West's contempt for Africa must end. Interestingly, the land reform in Zimbabwe could have formed a model for South Africa and Namibia, but political will is lacking. There have been many despots in Africa who owe their unremarkable rules to the support of western powers. It is ironic that the same western powers that preach democracy and the rule of law at home would see nothing wrong in supporting dictatorship and bad governance abroad if doing so served their economic and national interests.

Conclusions

Colonialism on the African continent was exploitative and brutal. The political and economic effects are far-reaching and will continue to affect the lives of millions of people on the continent. On the political scale, colonialism was undemocratic and autocratic and could not have provided a democratic role model for the people of Africa. The spate of undemocratic military regimes in Sub-Saharan Africa may not be unconnected with this. In some places, like Kenya and Cote d'Ivoire, elections tend to be marred by acrimony and violence, a pointer to the fact that the democratic culture is not deep. It is a truism that colonialism created artificial borders, lumping diverse peoples together. One of the consequences of artificial borders is that in some post-colonial multi-ethnic societies, the state machinery becomes dominated by a single communal group or a coalition of a few communal groups that are unresponsive to the needs and yearnings of other groups in society.

In the 20th century, colonialism transformed into neo-colonialism, reflecting the desire of former colonial masters to hang onto their former colonies. It represents imperialism in its final and most dangerous stage (Nkrumah, 1965). This is because neo-colonialism is subtle and indirect. It breeds dependency, as evidenced in unequal trade and balance of payments. African countries continue to be producers of primary products rather than manufacturers of finished goods. The manifestations of bad governance, such as corruption, lack of transparency, lack of accountability, and disregard for the rule of law, can be traced back to the nature of colonialism. Currently, they all feed and strengthen neo-colonialism.

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The nature of leadership and legitimacy in the former colonies is such that former colonial masters arrogated to themselves the power of determining the leaders that emerge. Moderates are preferred over the so-called extremists because of the belief that, in their hands, the political and economic interests of former colonial masters would be preserved. These pliant leaders often collude with western interests to despoil their countries. This has been at the core of the leadership vacuum or failure in post-colonial Africa and a contributing factor in the continent's underdevelopment.

Globalisation has variously been seen as an interdependence of nations and also as an instrument of neo-colonialism because emerging economies are accepted into it from a subjugated position (Akinboye 2008; Khor 2000). Consequently, dependency theorists advocated for the delinking of Third World economies from the international capitalist system to foster true development (Ake 1981; Frank 1976). This is easier said than done, as the world economic system tends to be intertwined. African economies would do well to engage the world economic system on their own terms. This calls for political will and self-reliance. It also calls for a shift in paradigm to engage with development partners in other spheres and climes who are willing to place the development of these societies side by side with their own economic and political interests.

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